

Polyphenol—Protein Reactions and Their Significance for Agricultural Practices

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THE primary valence chemical reactions in which polyphenols may be implicated nearly always involve, first of all, the oxidation of an *o*-diphenol to a quinonoid compound.

This may sometimes be spontaneous, but is often accomplished by a copper enzyme, also using atmospheric oxygen; in either case hydrogen peroxide is likely to be formed¹. The same enzyme also appears capable of hydroxylating an aromatic ring *ortho* to a preexisting phenolic group, as in the formation of dopa from tyrosine. The exact mechanism of oxidizing an *o*-diphenol to an *o*-quinone seems to be variable instead of a 2-electron step leading directly to the quinone, a semiquinone radical anion may arise as the intermediate in two single-electron steps. It is strange also that, with all the new physical techniques which have become available during the 20th century, nobody seems yet to have established firmly the structure of the colourless form of *o*-benzoquinone, discovered by Wills-tatter in 1908, and tentatively assigned by him a peroxide structure^{2,3}.

As far as concerns the reactions which I am going to discuss, these quinonoids, being some of the least stable compounds known to organic chemistry, are mainly postulated as intermediates and scarcely ever isolated. The results of using "trapping reagents", such as benzenesulphonic acid, to identify them may prove equivocal, as Davies and Pierpoint⁴ showed, when they found the locus of substitution to depend certainly on the solvent medium, and perhaps also on binding by an enzyme.

Oxidative self-polymerisation of quinonoids can be quite chaotic⁵. Diphenyl bonds can arise—a good example is dityrosine, a normal constituent of insect wing-hinge protein⁶. For ether-bond formation, the biosynthetic dimerization of *N*-coumaroyl-agnatite to hordatine, an antifungal principle in barley, is a good simple example. Of course, both these kinds of condensations are believed to occur during the biosynthesis of lignin from substituted cinnamic acids or alcohols, but it is less likely there

that *o*-diphenolic compounds are involved. Fused isocyclic rings may also arise, particularly by ring-sidechain condensation of cinnamic derivatives; detailed examples are scarce, e.g. dihydroguaiaretic acid and colchicine. Naphthalene occurs in various essential oils, and may have a similar origin. Nicolaus⁶ believes the seed-coat melanoidins, and some other dark pigments of plants, to be formed similarly, by oxidative polymerisation of nitrogen-free *o*-diphenols, such as protocatechuic acid.

Now let us turn to reactions of *o*-quinonoids with the main functional groups found in proteins. Coupling with the phenolic group of *tyrosine* has already been mentioned⁶, although it is not yet clear which of the polyphenol oxidases can attack tyrosine residues bound in peptide linkage.

The thiol group (*cysteine*) seems to undergo the simplest reactions—direct coupling to the aromatic ring, giving a thioether diphenol stabilized by its modified oxidation-reduction potential against further oxidative coupling. But very little is known about *direct* oxidative effects of quinonoids (and the accompanying hydrogen peroxide), and the extent to which resultant disulphide, sulphenic, sulphinic or sulphonic groups may be formed. Sulphinic groups, if formed, would couple readily with the quinonoid nucleus to form a sulphone derivative.

The thioether group (*methionine*) has been shown to couple readily with the aromatic nucleus to give sulphonium derivatives, but these have only been formed in relatively acid environments^{6a-c,8}. To what extent quinonoids or peroxides will oxidize methionine residues to dehydromethionine, methionine sulphoxides or methionine sulphone does not seem to be known, nor whether any of these groups, if formed, would undergo coupling with *o*-quinonoids.

Oxidative attack on the indole nucleus of *tryptophan* residues is likewise a possibility, as indole itself is attacked by *o*-quinones³.

With amino groups (in proteins chiefly the ϵ -amino groups of *lysine* residues) coupling to the aromatic nucleus occurs, with repeated possible

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additions of up to three amino groups, to give the tautomeric main products elucidated by Roger Davies⁷. The intermediate diphenols have such oxidation-reduction potentials that, unlike the thiol coupling products, they are further oxidized by excess of the initial *o*-quinone to give further complicated coloured products, many of which are polymeric. Davies⁷ observed up to 50 such compounds on coupling *o*-benzoquinone with simple aliphatic amines. Caffeoquinone seemed to give a simpler mixture, including a very striking blue compound, whose exact structure remains to be determined⁸. This may throw some light on the blue and green colours arising during alkaline treatment of such chlorogenic acid and protein-rich materials as sunflower-seed meal^{9,10}, as well as on a blue reaction product between potato virus X and chlorogenoquinone¹⁵.

In the case of enzymic oxidation of *free tyrosine and dopa*, self cyclisation of dopaquinone to the indoline cyclodopa occurs. This is further oxidized to "dopachrome", which can polymerize to give melanins⁶. Interesting couplings of these intermediates with thiols lead to the red and brown pigments of hair and feathers¹¹. In our laboratory in Norwich, where enzymic browning of potatoes has been much studied and correlated quantitatively with the content of free tyrosine in the tuber, we got the impression that the reaction involves mainly this self-polymerization of free tyrosine, with little attack on lysine ϵ -amino groups of the tuber proteins. However, tubers of a potato variety poor in free tyrosine and rich in chlorogenic acid gave yellowing rather than browning, with indications of attack on the lysine ϵ -amino groups of the protein¹². I will say more about this later.

Horigome¹⁷ has claimed that *o*-quinonoids can attack *peptide bonds* because the nutritive value of acetylated casein was diminished by their presence, but Davies and Frahn⁷ using *N*-methylacetamide as a model compound, were unable to show that it had any reaction with *o*-benzoquinone.

That seems to be about all that is yet known about reactions of *o*-quinonoids with the functional groups of proteins. The important thing to note is that it is the sidechains of the nutritionally essential amino acids *tyrosine, tryptophan, cysteine, cystine, methionine* and *lysine* that must be expected to undergo alteration.

Consequences of these chemical reactions having importance for agricultural practices :

Pierpoint¹⁴ has published an excellent review of the various biological consequences of these reactions, so I can be very brief. It has often been claimed that oxidizing *o*-diphenols have a direct effect on virus infectivity. However, in a concrete example studied by Pierpoint and colleagues¹⁵, potato virus X retained some infectivity when as many as

two of its lysine ϵ -amino groups had coupled with chlorogenic acid residues. There seems little disagreement that oxidizing polyphenols play a role in the necrotizing reaction which protects the plant against a variety of parasites.

In wilting leaves, such reactions set in throughout the tissue, and they have been studied in some detail in connection with the manufacture of black tea and the curing of tobacco, about which last I will have more to say later. It seems to follow that such reactions will also be liable to occur in "green-crop fractionation"¹⁶, and will affect adversely the feeding value of the protein-rich fraction separated for monogastric animals. This seems to have first been demonstrated explicitly ten years ago by Horigome and Kandatsu¹⁷. Also, in our own laboratory, we have shown for a range of leaf-protein concentrates (L.P.C's), that nutritional value, total lysine obtained on acid hydrolysis and 'available lysine' can diminish in parallel from the values typical for carefully prepared L.P.C's¹⁸. It is generally recommended, in isolating such L.P.C's, to heat quickly, to inactivate enzymes and to add sulphite, for reduction of any quinonoids which may tend to form.

Nevertheless, the drying of L.P.C's may well reactivate quinonoid-protein reactions, and there seems a *prima-facie* case for feeding the L.P.C. slurries directly to pigs, without first drying them. The phytochemical literature is curiously deficient in information about the polyphenols present in the various forage crops now being considered for green-crop fractionation, and a survey by some of the improved modern quantitative and qualitative procedures¹⁹ seems desirable. As far as concerns the fibrous residue, which is to be fed to ruminant animals, the opposite considerations may apply, as protein that has been crosslinked and rendered insoluble is likely to resist premature microbial attack in the rumen^{19a}. Similar effects have been encountered by Jones and Mangan²⁰ in studying the relative utilization by cows of the protein of sainfoin (*Onobrychis viciifolia*) and of other forage legumes. The sainfoin is of higher polyphenol content and its protein seems to be better utilized.

Similar considerations about insolubilisation of the protein of wilted or senescent leaves may apply to transfer of nitrogen between legumes and associated forage plants. While in Australia recently, I learnt that it has proved very difficult, in the tropical regions, to find any legume which would pass the nitrogen fixed by it to the associated grasses as efficiently as this occurs in the clover-ryegrass leys of the temperate regions of the world. In some cases, this effect was thought attributable to the high content of polyphenols, in the legume leaf, which would react with the leaf protein to give something similar to soil humic acid, rendering the nitrogen and sulphur of the leaf protein only slowly mineralizable in the soil.

In such cases, the benefits of the legume-grass association may only develop after the ley has been established for several years.

Some years ago, I suggested that one of the main evolutionary pressures that have led to the accumulation of the simpler polyphenols in plants has been so that fallen leaves and other decayed plant material should build up soil organic matter that would be beneficial to the plant or to its descendants²¹.

There seems, from isotope dating experiments, to be some general agreement that the "aromatic" moiety of humic acids is more persistent than the "protein" moiety—one can picture an aromatic "core" slowly quinonizing as it weathers away and coupling repeatedly with protein newly introduced into the soil. The flow of carbon and nitrogen through the soil organic matter has recently been reviewed at length by Oades and Ladd²². In quantitative terms, one would expect that one of the main points of attachment of protein to such aromatic moieties would be the ϵ -amino groups of lysine residues. It is therefore interesting that in more heavily tilled soils or in regions where the soil is exposed to particularly severe weathering, the proportion of lysine to total amino acids increases at the same time as the total-nitrogen content of the humic acids decreases²¹.

A tendency of the free amino groups of an oligopeptide to react with quinones in such a way that the parent amino acid can be only partially recovered by acid hydrolysis has been demonstrated^{23,24}.

Perry and Adams²⁵ have demonstrated the same phenomenon by reacting oligopeptides with natural humic acid. Piper and Posner²⁶ showed that extra amino acid could be released from humic acid by acid hydrolysis after peroxide treatment, and showed that this was consistent with involvement of the amino group in a quinone-imine (Schiff base-type) linkage. Cranwell and Haworth²⁴ emphasized that an amino group substituted on the aromatic nucleus of a quinone is effectively involved in a vinylogous-amide linkage. Both these types of linkage should be susceptible, at least partially, to hydrolysis by acid and by alkali.

Simonart and colleagues²⁷ isolated from humic acid, by extraction with phenol, a small proportion of the nitrogen as typical protein. They showed by electrophoresis that much of the rest of the nitrogen of the humic acid was in a more electro-negative state. Moreover, the less the nitrogen content of the humic acid, the smaller was the proportion of it which could be extracted as typical protein. Very similar results were obtained by Biederbech and Paul²⁸. All this evidence is strongly suggestive of the involvement of amino groups of proteins by primary-valence linkages during the building up of soil organic matter.

Detailed studies of involvement of lysine ϵ -amino groups with quinonoids:

Because L.P.C's are usually fed to monogastric animals as supplements to a basal cereal diet, their content of 'available lysine' is usually critical. It was with this in mind, as well as the considerations about soil organic matter which I have just mentioned, that my colleagues in Norwich and I have undertaken a more detailed study of the involvement of lysine ϵ -amino groups with quinonoids.

For our experiments the tobacco leaf proved very suitable, since it has a single predominant polyphenol in high concentration, namely chlorogenic acid, and the leaf proteins have been particularly well characterized, initially by Wildman and his colleagues, who discovered "Fraction I protein" in tobacco.

We measured chlorogenic acid as quinic acid released by cold alkali, using the colorimetric periodate-thio-barbiturate technique. In this way we were able to show²⁹ that, when a leaf is ground up and allowed to autolyse and go brown in the air, the chlorogenic acid which is initially in the low-molecular fraction (presumably free) migrates into the bulk-protein fraction, which undergoes a parallel diminution in its total and 'chemically available' lysine content. We further used chromatographic techniques and mass spectrometry to confirm that quinic acid is released by hydrolysis from the bulk-protein fraction of browned tobacco leaves³⁰. Similar effects had been demonstrated by our colleague E. I. Mbadiwe during normal storage of the West African oilseed *Pentaclethra macrophylla*^{30,31}.

In this case, they were mediated by the phenolic alkaloid *N*-caffeoylputrescine, which is abundantly present in the seed³².

We have also tried to obtain direct chemical evidence about the mode of linkage of quinonoid with lysine moieties. Emil Fischer prepared the first amino-acid-quinonoid coupling product, namely that of *p*-benzoquinone with glycine ester³³; similar derivatives have been prepared by W.T.J. Morgan³⁴ and by Cranwell and Haworth²⁴. As I have already explained, such derivatives are susceptible to hydrolysis, also to rearrangement under the hydrolysis conditions, with some evolution of ammonia.

The approach tried by us at Norwich was to try to stabilize the linkage against hydrolysis and rearrangement by hydrogenation of the aromatic moiety to a cyclohexane derivative. We managed to do this successfully with a number of model compounds, using rhodium on alumina as catalyst in 70% acetic acid at room temperature and pressure³⁵. There was some hydrogenolysis of amino and hydroxyl groups from the cyclohexane nuclei, but it was never complete. Moreover, work with the aminocyclitol antibiotics has shown this

class of compounds to be remarkably stable to boiling with strong acids. The aromatic groups of intact proteins hydrogenated well under our conditions. Unfortunately, sulphur in thiol and thio-ether groups was removed hydrogenolytically from the carbon skeleton, so the method cannot be used for studying reactions of quinonoids with the sulphur-containing amino acids. However, the reaction appears promising for studying the mode of blockage of the lysine sidechains. We have hydrogenated the protein fraction of aerobically autolysed tobacco leaves (and of cigars). On hydrolysis, these give a series of novel chromatographic peaks additional to those that we have identified as derivatives of the common amino acids in hydrogenated fresh tobacco-leaf protein (and different also from the quinic acid derivatives already identified)⁵⁶. We do not yet have any structural evidence about the new compounds, but there seems a good chance that some of them may turn out to be lysine derivatives. Weybrew and Long⁵⁷ recognized homocitrulline, α -amino adipic acid and what they simply called a "metabolite of lysine" in hydrolysed fractions from cured tobacco, but do not seem yet to have published any detailed identifications.

Conclusion :

I have said enough now, I hope, to convince you that this complicated group of chemical reactions plays a big role in a number of matters important to agricultural practice—particularly in plant protection, in animal nutrition and in the functioning of the organic matter of the soil. In the past, these reactions have not been a popular study with organic chemists, owing to the extreme complexity of the courses which they take. I hope that more chemists, encouraged by the newer physical techniques that are available, will be attracted in the coming years to take up such studies. What is most needed in the immediate present is, as a starting point, a much better picture of the distribution of the simpler polyphenols among plants of agronomic importance. That is something which, using modern techniques¹⁹, the phytochemists can give us quite quickly and with relatively little effort.

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